

BIOLOGICAL VALUE OF THE PROTEINS OF *CICER ARIETINUM* (BENGAL GRAM) AND *CAJANUS INDICUS* (ARHAR) BY THE BALANCE-SHEET AND GROWTH METHODS.

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The biological value of proteins of *Cicer arietinum* (Bengal gram) and *Cajanus indicus* (Arhar) was determined by the balance-sheet method and by the growth of young rats. In the balance-sheet experiments, *Cicer arietinum* has a higher biological value than the value of *Cajanus indicus*. In the growth method, the growth of rat per gramme of protein intake produced by *Cicer arietinum* at 15 per cent concentration of protein is less than the corresponding value for *Cajanus indicus*, while at lower concentrations of proteins, *Cicer arietinum* produces more growth.

Investigations on the biological values and chemical analysis of proteins of different varieties of rice, pulse and fish have been pursued for a number of years in this laboratory (Basu *et al.*, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1936, **23**, 789, 811 ; 1937, **24**, 1001, 1043, 1067 ; 1938, **26**, 177, 191). These investigations have shown that *Aman* rice proteins are much superior to *Aus* rice proteins in promoting growth, that Ruhee (*Labeo rohita*) proteins are of a better quality than Hilsa (*Clupea ilisa*) proteins and that contrary to the popular belief, proteins of green gram have higher biological value than those of lentil and produce much more rapid growth in young rats than the latter. It has been found that *Lathyrus sativa*, while not of much value in promoting growth, induces no lathyrism in rats. The biological value of different pulses has been found to be different and in some cases pulses, which appear to be equally efficient in maintaining nitrogenous equilibrium, behaved quite differently in promoting growth. The present investigation deals with the nutritive value of the two common pulses *Cicer arietinum* (Bengal gram) and *Cajanus indicus* (Arhar). The experiments were carried out with rats and the technique employed in both the balance-sheet and growth methods was the same as followed in previous investigations from this laboratory.

The composition of the pulses used as sources of protein is given in Table I and that of the diets in Table II.

TABLE I.

Analysis of pulses used as sources of protein.

Pulse:	Moisture.	Total N.	Protein N × 6.25	Ether extractive.	Ash.	Crude fibre.	Carbohydrate by diff.
<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	15.11%	3.82%	23.87%	5.75%	2.83%	3.24%	49.20%
<i>Cajanus indicus</i>	10.35	3.87	24.19	1.89	3.35	1.01	59.21

TABLE II.

Composition of diets.

Constituents of diets.	Nitrogen-free.	<i>Cicer arietinum.</i> <i>Cajanus indicus.</i>					
		Percentage of protein (approx.) in diet.					
		5%.	10%.	15%.	5%.	10%.	15%.
<i>Cicer arietinum</i>	0 g.	126 g.	252 g.	378 g.	...	...	...
<i>Cajanus indicus</i>	0	...	...	...	129 g.	259 g.	388 g.
Chopped sugar	90	54	54	54	54	54	54
Ghee (butter fat)	100	65	58	50	72	72	72
Cod liver oil	20	12	12	12	12	12	12
Salt mixture	50	24	24	24	24	24	24
Calcium carbonate	8	6	6	6	6	6	6
Corn starch	735	313	194	76	303	173	44

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The Balance-sheet Method.

Typical data regarding the metabolism experiments and calculations of the biological values for 10% protein level of the two pulses *Cicer arietinum* and *Cajanus indicus* proteins in the diet are indicated in Tables III and IV. The results of experiments at different concentrations of proteins in the diet are summarised in Table V

TABLE III.

Balance-sheet experiments with proteins of Cicer arietinum.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages.)

Rat No.	Weight Initial.	Weight Final.	Intake Food.	Nitrogen Nitrogen.	Nitrogen Faecal.	Nitrogen Metabolic.	Food nitrogen In faeces.	Food nitrogen Absorbed
Experiments with nitrogen-free diet.								
575	197 g.	195.5 g.	12.0 g.	...	13.54 mg.	*1.13 mg.	...	...
576	212	211.4	12.0	...	16.54	*1.38	...	..
577	215	212.8	10.2	...	12.95	*1.27	...	...
578	198	196.6	8.8	...	14.15	*1.61	...	...
579	217	216.1	11.9	...	17.52	*1.47	...	..
580	194	188.4	11.2	...	22.02	*1.97	...	...
Experiments with 10% <i>Cicer arietinum</i> protein.								
575	195 g.	196.4 g.	13.5 g.	227.61 mg.	47.73 g.	15.26 g.	32.47 mg.	195.14 mg.
576	215	215.8	13.5	227.61	56.31	18.63	37.68	189.93
577	215	216.2	14.1	237.61	45.38	17.91	27.47	210.14
578	199	201.2	13.0	217.42	48.04	20.93	27.11	190.31
579	219	219.7	13.2	218.18	60.53	19.40	41.13	187.05
580	195	197.3	12.2	203.76	61.41	24.03	37.38	166.38
Rat No.	Digestibility.	Mean digestibility.	Urinary N Total.	Urinary N Endogenous.	Food nitrogen in urine.	Food nitrogen Utilised.	Biological value (B.V.)	Mean B.V.
Experiments with nitrogen free-diet.								
575	...	...	...	32.58 mg.	...	...	...	...
576	...	...	...	32.46	...	...	...	...
577	...	...	...	37.70	...	...	...	...
578	...	...	...	31.21	...	...	...	...
579	..	...	...	47.73	...	...	...	...
580	...	...	...	44.97	...	...	...	...
Experiments with 10% <i>Cicer arieinum</i> proteint.								
575	86		123.83 mg.	32.58 mg.	91.25 mg.	103.89 mg.	53	
576	83		118.01	32.46	85.55	104.38	54	
877	88	85	142.17	37.70	104.47	105.67	50	52
578	88		127.30	31.21	96.09	94.22	50	
579	82		133.69	47.73	85.96	101.09	54	
580	82		125.40	44.97	80.43	85.95	52	

* per g, of food intake.

TABLE IV.

Balance-sheet experiments with proteins of Cajanus indicus.

(Figures of intake and excretion represent daily averages).

Rat No.	Weight		Intake		Nitrogen		Food	
	Initial.	Final.	Food.	Nitrogen.	Faecal.	Metabolic.	In faeces.	Absorbed.

Experiments with nitrogen-free ration.

581	218 g.	216'4 g	9'4 g.	..	17'21 mg	*1'84 mg	...	...
582	322	319'2	13'2	...	18'67	*1'42	...	...
583	304	301'6	13'0	...	20'39	*1'56	...	...
584	286	284'2	12'5	...	22'43	*1'79	...	...
585	254	252'4	10'8	...	16'18	*1'50	...	...
586	235	232'1	11'4	...	21'55	*1'89	...	...

Experiments with 10% *Cajanus indicus* protein.

581	217 g.	218'5 g.	9'5 g.	158'85 mg.	35'79 mg.	17'48 mg.	18'31 mg.	140'54 mg.
582	324	324'6	13'4	210'37	33'68	19'03	14'65	195'72
583	309	309'9	14'5	229'66	40'93	22'62	18'31	211'35
584	291	289'3	14'4	228'43	41'69	25'78	15'91	212'52
585	261	262'8	11'0	180'08	32'61	16'50	16'11	163'97
586	239	238'6	12'7	205'16	40'48	24'00	16'48	188'68

Experiments with nitrogen-free ration.

Rat No.	Digesti- bility.	Mean digesti- bility	Urinary N		Food nitrogen in urine.	Biologi- cal vaule (B. V.)	Mean B. V.
			Total.	Endoge- nous.			
581	...	...	...	38'14 mg.	...	...	...
582	...	..	...	51'78	...	...	...
583	...	...	...	54'25	...	...	...
584	...	...	...	42'72	...	...	...
585	...	...	...	44'69	...	...	...
586	...	...	...	49'36	...	...	...

Experiments with 10% *Cajanus indicus* protein.

581	88		109'67 mg	38'14 mg.	71'53 mg.	69'01 mg.	49	
582	93		161'25	51'78	109'47	86'25	44	
583	92	92	168'18	54'25	113'93	97'42	46	46
584	93		146'66	42'72	103'94	108'58	51	
585	91		137'52	44'69	92'83	71'14	43	
586	92		154'45	49'36	105'39	83'09	44	

* per g. of food intake,

TABLE V.

Biological value and Digestibility of proteins of Cicer arietinum and Cajanus indicus.

Material.	Rat No.	Body wt.	Percentage of proteins in the diet.					
			5%.		10%.		15%.	
			B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.	B.V.	D.
C. A r i e t i n u m .	575	197 g.	59	80	53	86	41	90
	576	212	57	87	54	83	46	89
	577	215	59	83	50	88	43	86
	578	198	61	84	50	88	49	84
	579	217	58	87	54	82	46	90
	580	194	64	86	52	82	48	86
	Average			60	85	52	85	46
C. I n d i c u s .	581	218	53	75	49	88	32	82
	582	322	57	76	44	93	37	84
	583	304	52	73	46	92	36	84
	584	286	56	78	51	93	34	82
	585	254	59	74	43	91	41	84
	586	235	54	77	44	92	34	82
	Average			55	76	46	92	36

The mean biological value (B.V.), digestibility (D) and protein values of proteins of different pulses at 10% level of proteins determined in this laboratory are summarised in Table VI for the sake of comparison.

TABLE VI.

Pulse.	Protein content	Mean biological value.	Mean digestibility.	Mean protein value.
	P.	B.V.	D.	$= P \times \frac{B.V.}{100} \times \frac{D}{100}$
<i>Lens esculenta</i> (Lentil) ...	22.60 %.	32	90	6.5
<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> (Green gram)	23.26	52	86	10.4
<i>Glycine hispida</i> (Soya bean) ...	41.20	58	85	20.2
<i>Lathyrus sattva</i> (Khesari) ...	32.20	50	90	14.4
<i>Pisum sattva</i> (Field pea) ...	27.10	48	91	11.7
<i>Cicer arietinum</i> (Bengal gram)	23.87	52	85	10.6
<i>Cajanus indicus</i> (Arhar) ...	24.19	46	92	10.2

The Growth Method

The quality of the two pulses has also been determined by the growth produced in young growing rats per g. of protein intake over a period of four and eight weeks. The levels of protein intake and the composition of diets were the same as in the balance-sheet experiments. The same method was adopted as was done in previous investigations in this laboratory. The growths obtained and the biological values (B.D.)

$\left[\frac{\text{gain in weight (g.)}}{\text{protein intake (g.)}} \right]$ at 10 per cent protein level are indicated in Table

VII and the results at different protein concentrations are summarised in Table VIII.

TABLE VII.

Growth experiments with proteins of *Cicer arietinum* and *Cajanus indicus* at 10% protein level.

Rat No.	Sex.	Initial weight.	Four weeks.			Eight weeks.			Mean B. V.	Mean B. V.
			Intake Food.	Intake Protein.	Gain in wt.	*B. V.	Intake Food.	Intake Protein.		
10% <i>Cicer arietinum</i> protein in diet.										
520	Female	50 g.	183.4 g.	18.34 g.	23.5 g.	1.3	382.2 g.	38.22 g.	45.0 g.	1.2
521	Male	50	205.2	20.52	36.0	1.7	508.4	50.84	72.0	1.4
522	Male	50	196.0	19.60	31.0	1.6	434.5	43.45	65.5	1.5
523	Female	50	180.3	18.03	25.5	1.4	452.8	45.28	51.0	1.1
524	Female	45.5	165.8	16.58	23.0	1.4	395.6	39.56	52.5	1.3
525	Female	48.5	148.5	14.85	23.5	1.6	413.7	41.37	48.0	1.2
10% <i>Cajanus indicus</i> protein.										
555	Male	47.5	192.4	19.24	27.0	1.4	403.8	40.38	44.5	1.1
556	Female	46.5	168.7	16.87	21.5	1.3	346.5	34.65	28.0	0.8
557	Female	42.0	174.5	17.45	24.5	1.4	384.9	38.49	38.0	1.0
558	Male	43.5	183.5	18.35	27.5	1.5	414.6	41.46	49.5	1.2
559	Male	41.0	191.3	19.13	26.0	1.4	422.3	42.23	42.0	1.0
660	Male	47.5	178.7	17.87	26.5	1.5	365.7	36.57	40.5	1.1

* B. V. = Gain in wt./protein intake.

TABLE VIII.

Mean biological values of proteins of *C. arietinum* and *C. indicus* by the growth method.

Protein in the diet.	Number of rats.	Period of experiments.	Increase in weight Variation.	Mean.	Total food intake (dry). Variation.	Mean.	Protein intake (mean).	B.V.
<i>Cicer arietinum</i> , ₂								
5	6	4 (weeks).	10.5-15.5 g.	12.8 g.	142.8-162.9 g.	153.7 g.	7.68 g.	1.7
0	8		8.5-15.5	11.3	238.4-296.4	275.0	13.5	0.8
15	6	4	23.0-36.0	27.1	148.5-205.2	179.9	18.0	1.5
	8		45.0-72.0	55.7	382.2-568.4	431.2	43.1	1.3
	6	4	25.5-44.5	34.3	163.8-183.5	173.5	26.0	1.3
	8		41.0-80.0	60.7	327.9-403.0	358.3	53.7	1.1
<i>Carjanus indicus</i> .								
5	6	4	(-4.0) - 1.5	0.4	116.0-140.7	131.7	6.59	...
0	8		(-4.5) - 0.5	2.4	245.1-280.2	266.9	13.4	...
15	6	4	21.5-27.5	25.5	168.7-192.4	181.5	18.2	1.4
	8		28.0-49.5	40.4	346.5-422.2	389.6	39.0	1.0
	6	4	39.5-52.0	45.3	166.8-192.5	179.6	27.0	1.7
	8		63.5-91.0	75.2	341.3-382.5	363.1	54.5	1.4

For the sake of comparison the biological values of the proteins of the different pulses by the growth method worked out in this laboratory are given in Table IX.

TABLE IX.

Pulse,	Growth per g. of protein intake after	
	four weeks.	eight weeks.
<i>Lens esculenta</i> (Lentil)	1.1	0.9
<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> (green Gram)	1.4	1.2
<i>Lathyrus sativa</i> (Khesari)	0.6	No growth
<i>Glycine hispida</i> (Soya bean)	1.9	1.5
<i>Pisum sativum</i> (Field pea)	1.5	0.9
<i>Cicer arietinum</i> (Bengal gram)	1.5	1.3
<i>Cajanus indicus</i> (Arhar)	1.4	1.0

DISCUSSION.

Results obtained indicate that the proteins of *Cicer arietinum* are superior to those of *Cajanus indicus* both for the maintenance of nitrogen balance as well as for promoting growth in young rats, though the latter contains a higher percentage of protein than the former. With respect to biological value, digestibility and protein value *Cicer arietinum* is as efficient as *Phaseolus mungo*. The biological value of *Cajanus indicus* is rather low, being higher than that of *Lens esculenta* only but the digestibility of the proteins of *Lens esculenta* is higher than those of *Cajanus indicus*.

In the growth experiments the proteins of *Cicer arietinum* caused appreciable growth at 5% level of intake, while the proteins of *Cajanus indicus* at the same concentration produced little or no growth. It is evident that the proteins of *Cajanus indicus* are deficient in one or more of the essential amino-acids. At 10% level of intake also, the proteins of *Cicer arietinum* are superior to those of *Cajanus indicus*. It is interesting to note that at 15% level of intake, the proteins of *Cicer arietinum* are inferior to those of *Cajanus indicus* in promoting growth, though the food intake was almost the same in both the cases. The reason is not quite clear, but it may be possible that though *Cicer arietinum* proteins are superior to those of *Cajanus indicus*, probably the former may contain in minute amounts some factor which inhibits growth. The action of this growth-inhibitory factor is not

so marked at lower concentration of the pulse in the diet but may become appreciable at higher concentrations. Growth per g. of protein intake with *Cicer arietinum* increases from 0.8 at 5% protein level to 1.3 at 10% level because 5% protein in the diet are quite an insufficient amount of protein and the effect of the toxin is more than counterbalanced by the increase in protein intake. As the percentage of protein is, however, increased to 15, growth per g. of protein intake decreases to 1.1 very probably due to the effect of the growth-inhibitory factor. With *Cajanus indicus* growth per g. of protein-intake continually increases from 0 to 1.4 as the percentage of protein in the diet increases from 5 to 15.

C O N C L U S I O N

The biological values of proteins of *Cicer arietinum* by the balance-sheet method at 5, 10 and 15% levels of feeding are 60, 52 and 46 respectively. The corresponding values for *Cajanus indicus* are 55, 46 and 36. *Cicer arietinum* has thus a higher biological value than *Cajanus indicus* at all levels of intake and with a particular pulse the biological value decreases with increase in concentration of protein in the diet.

The mean digestibilities of the protein of *Cicer arietinum* at 5, 10 and 15% levels of intake are 85, 85 and 88 respectively and the corresponding values for *Cajanus indicus* are 76, 92 and 83. The protein values of *Cicer arietinum* and *Cajanus indicus* [at 10% level of intake are practically identical, the values being 10.6 and 10.2 respectively.

Growth per g. of protein ingested at 15% protein concentration in the diet is for *Cicer arietinum* 1.1 and for *Cajanus indicus*, 1.4. With 10% protein the corresponding values for *Cicer arietinum* and *Cajanus indicus* are 1.3 and 1.0 respectively. With 5% concentration of protein growth per g. of protein ingested is 0.8 in the case of *Cicer arietinum* while *Cajanus indicus* does not produce any growth at that concentration. *Cicer arietinum* may contain traces of a growth-inhibitory factor which makes its presence felt at higher intakes of proteins.